

THE PROBLEM OF MALNUTRITION AMONG YOUNG CHILDREN ON THE AFRICAN CONTINENT AND THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VARIOUS INFECTIOUS DISEASES IN THE REGION

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Abstract: This article discusses the problems of hunger and epidemics of malnutrition among young children in the countries of the African continent. Opinions are expressed about epidemics and various infectious diseases in the region.

Key words: Children, hunger, epidemic, South Africa, Kwashiorkor, diet

In the countries of the world today, the problem of malnutrition among young children is one of the main problems on the agenda. rich rural groups lead a farming lifestyle that allows them to survive only on the very limited resources provided by their land. The food resources they have are lacking in several essential nutrients, so malnutrition is more common among these people, pastoral people and other people with other animal-based diets. Compared to the average American diet, rural South African groups such as the Bantu eat a diet with less than half the fat content.[30]

A lack of fat is often accompanied by a lack of protein. A lack of protein in the South African diet can lead to severe nutritional deficiency "kwashiorkor." Studies have been conducted comparing the frequency of kwashiorkor among five African groups: Maasai, Kikuyu, Batussi, Bahutu, Pieraerts, and Wakamba. The Masai are a pastoral people who eat milk and sometimes meat. The Wakamba, Kikuyu and Bahutu are non-pastoral agricultural people who grow the food they eat. Batussi people, herders, consume a lot of cheese milk. The Pieraert people are lake dwellers who eat fresh fish and dried fish.

As a result of the study, kwashiorkor disease was not detected among the Masai, Batussi, Pieraert and a small part of the Bahutu, who grow beans in addition

to vegetables and grains. However, many cases of kwashiorkor have been found among the Wakamba, Kiyuku, and Bahutu, who eat only grains and vegetables. This suggests that people in South Africa, whose lifestyles are based on agriculture, are at high risk of malnutrition. . Outside of devastated rural areas, South Africans live in the evenings and others in poverty-stricken conditions with access to only a high-starch, low-protein diet. A diet that is not usually eaten in South Africa is based on the staples of rice, porridge and maize. Poverty. Malnutrition is the main cause of poverty. According to the 2000 statistics, 50% of South Africa's population is below the poverty line. South Africa's GDP per capita is \$11,000, but 21% of people live on a day or less. In 2008, 27.9% of youth between the ages of fifteen and twenty-four were unemployed, and the overall unemployment rate was even higher (33.2%). The unemployment rate stems in part from South Africa's unstable macroeconomic status, which is still effectively under control despite modern efforts. Economic instability at the national level creates income instability for many Africans, which is reflected in reduced food and beverage purchases. Statistics show that the share of income spent on food and drink in South Africa has fallen dramatically from 27.4% in 2000 to 16.6% in 2005. These statistics are reflected in the poverty-stricken South African households where major food suppliers must change their food consumption patterns to cope with economic instability. This is a harmful change that disrupts nutrition. According to 2008 statistics, South Africa is the third most unequal economy in the world. Widespread poverty in Africa can be traced to many factors. UNICEF says the main causes of malnutrition are "lack of adequate care for vulnerable groups such as household security, maternal and child care, health, education, water and environment and adequate human services, such as sanitation and housing. According to the World Factbook, listed apartheid South Africa according to its impact, Apartheid caused many of these problems, especially housing, health and education. helped create the lim Issues such as education (i.e. poor school performance, poor cognitive development) are directly related to malnutrition in children.

Apartheid and colonialism from South Africa, other African countries. South Africa has many rich natural resources like diamonds and gold. When diamonds and gold were discovered between 1867 and 1886, instead of creating vast wealth for the African people, it caused widespread dispersal. Boers (Dutch settlers). After their arrival, the Dutch forced black farmers to leave their land either as share owners or as farm workers. Subjugation from non-native groups South Africa a Republic. This period of subjugation eventually led to apartheid in South Africa in 1948 with the establishment of the National Party (the ruling political party at the time).

In the 1960s, apartheid-based governments created African reserves where blacks could live and have opportunities. "separate development." Although the majority of South Africans were (and continue to be) black, reserves violated a disproportionately small amount of land (13% of South Africa). The reserves were geographically isolated and had poor health, infrastructure and irrigation systems. Although the first multi-ethnic elections in 1994 brought an immediate end to Apartheid, the harmful effects of Apartheid in South Africa are still felt today.[38]

Today, the poorest South African provinces are the provinces that cover the former reserves of Africa (Eastern Cape, Limpopo Province and KwaZulu-Natal). These areas are particularly famous for their high levels of malnutrition compared to South Africa's high indicators. These Black areas have the highest rate of AIDS in South Africa - 13.6% of Black Africans in South Africa are infected with HIV, while only 0.3% of white people living in South Africa are infected.

72% of South Africa's population is considered poor, with 86.9% living in chronic poverty in rural areas KwaZulu-Natal lives in rural areas. While people living in affluent urban areas have a good nutritional status, people in rural and agricultural areas in South Africa do not have the most adequate diets. This is because affluent urban residents have better education and access to food. while their rural, chronically poor counterparts are less educated, less literate, and have limited access to food. In 1997, 900,000 households in official reserves had no arable land, 1.4 million had no livestock other than chickens, and 770,000 households had neither

arable land nor any other livestock. Unfortunately, many farmers who owned livestock had to sell their livestock to overcome poverty. All these lead to food insecurity among the rural poor, thereby leading to nutrient deficiencies.

Treatment Since the 1990s, the first Millennium Development Goal of the United Nations was made to eliminate world hunger and malnutrition. According to the United Nations, there are some steps that could be particularly helpful in combating malnutrition. It is estimated that by increasing the intake of vitamins A and C and improving breastfeeding practices, the world 2.4 million children's lives could be saved every year across South Africa. Since then, various programs have been established in South Africa to help achieve this, all with varying degrees of success. Integrated nutrition program

In line with the United Nations' mission, the South African Ministry of Health established the Integrated Nutrition Program in 1995. The INP focuses primarily on helping people at risk of malnutrition: children six years of age and younger, pregnant women, and lactating women. The main foci of INP are breastfeeding promotion, growth monitoring and promotion, food fortification, micronutrient supplementation, management of severe malnutrition in hospital, nutritional rehabilitation in communities and nutrition management during illness. addresses the crisis by providing nutrition education, nutrition counseling services, and support for specific diseases and indirect health services.

Since the establishment of the INP in 1995, the South African Code of International Marketing of Breast-milk Substitutes has promoted breastfeeding. The Code established the World Health Organization and UNICEF during the thirty-third World Health Assembly.[46] Focuses on feeding malnourished infants through the facilitation of breastfeeding and the appropriate use of breastfeeding substitutes only when absolutely necessary. Unfortunately, there has been a lull in code legislation. If adopted, intensive training should be developed for health workers in line with national breastfeeding guidelines so that they can refer individuals who are skeptical about the benefits of breastfeeding to their children. Extension of benefits for

pregnancy and maternity leave should be promoted to provide sufficient time and funds.

INP implemented growth monitoring in South Africa through the following measures: provision of growth cards to all caregivers of children under two years of age, continuous monitoring of growth and malnutrition, counseling of caregivers and growth. However, there are various shortcomings in Africa's approach to monitoring and promoting growth. These include inaccurate weight assessment, lack of weight determination, inadequate training of nurses to detect deficiency, failure to provide growth charts to all infants, and insufficient communication with caregivers.

To directly address nutrient deficiencies, the INP established a mandatory food fortification program in 2003, which is linked to a micronutrient supplementation program.[45] However, the programs have not achieved the expected levels of success.[45] The Food Fortification Program created a food fortification mix that was incorporated into cornmeal and other complementary foods. The high folate content of the mixture eliminates folate deficiency. Since 1995, the food fortification program has mandated the iodization of salt. This seems to have stopped the incidence of iodine deficiency. However, any micronutrients that are not present in the food fortification mixture may still lead to overeating. Unfortunately, micronutrient supplementation programs have found it difficult to provide all of the micronutrient deficiencies to those in need. The software faces various limitations in the form of supply, supplement quality, bio-availability, distribution and compatibility. For example, the vitamin A supplement program has been criticized for struggling to reach the most vulnerable: children and postpartum women. By 2050, the world's population is expected to reach 9.7 billion, resulting in the poorest countries still live 7 years less than the United Nations estimates. In response to Covid:19 and to address these risks, the Food and Agriculture Organization calls on countries to:

Meeting the food needs of the population in need of social protection, developing social protection programs, continuing global food trade, maintaining

internal supply chain mechanisms, and increasing small farmers' food production support. Food security and malnutrition are at greater risk than ever in Africa and Asia. The 2015/2016 drought that hit Africa has since pushed them back, but the continent is making slow recoveries, but the drought still exists. The INP failed to recognize the challenges of managing severe malnutrition in hospital. South African hospitals admit many children with severe malnutrition, but most of these children die easily. was supposed to provide better mortality rates, but under-diagnosis of malnutrition-related deaths remains high. a significant decrease in mortality was observed.

To address the problem of nutritional supplementation at the community level, the INP helped establish a short-term program called the Nutrition Supplementation Program (formerly the PEM Scheme).[45] This program has become very effective due to the well-trained nutritionists assisting it. However, various shortcomings remain. The program struggled with community-based interventions and proper outreach and enrollment of all malnourished children without abusing resources for malnourished children. If the Child Support Grant were extended to cover all families of malnourished children, it would be possible to enroll children at risk in hospitals, clinics and other places involved in growth monitoring. .

Nutritional management during illness is another way to address malnutrition by INP. South Africa's Ministry of Health has adapted to this situation by promoting integrated management of childhood diseases and promoting proper nutrition management. UNICEF, together with the World Health Organization, established IMCI to improve child survival in low-resource areas. IMCI aims to achieve this by managing common childhood illnesses and improving nutrition and immunization practices. there are a variety of vague generalities that make it difficult to know for sure. This is problematic because the majority of sick children in South Africa are never seen by a nutritionist, so they have no other way of learning about proper nutrition.

Epidemiology affects individuals whose “food and nutrient intakes consistently do not meet individual requirements.” According to this definition, malnutrition is a widespread problem in South Africa. In 2000, 39% of the country's population suffered from malnutrition. This problem mostly affects children, especially young children. South Africa's malnutrition problem is typical of other countries' malnutrition problems, as South Africa is predominantly a young country, with one-third of the population under 15 years of age. Thus, in 2000, 25% of pre-school children and 20% of primary school students in South Africa suffered from malnutrition, which means that the future population of South Africa is at risk of malnutrition. Malnutrition in South Africa problem can be assessed separately by the deviation of each child's weight from the average weight for his age. According to the World Health Organization, the deviation from the average weight of children under five years of age in South Africa decreased from 31.5% to 8.7% from 1994 to 2008. Malnutrition can be assessed individually by deviating height from the average height for each child's age. This is because malnutrition stunts growth. The World Health Organization showed that over a thirteen-year period (1995 to 2008), the deviation from the average height of children under five in South Africa was slightly from 28.7% to 23.9% The decrease in the deviation indicates that the problem of malnutrition in South Africa has decreased in recent years. However, it remains a widespread problem, especially in the Eastern Cape and Limpopo region. These two areas are particularly poor and rural compared to the rest of South Africa. According to UNICEF, although 84.5% of South Africans have access to piped water, only 62.4% of Eastern Cape residents have piped water.

Also, while only 13.6% of South African households do not have a toilet, 30% of Eastern Cape residents do not have a shower. Similar statistics apply to the rural areas of the Limpopo province in the north of South Africa. The prevalence of malnutrition in Limpopo is so widespread that a 2005 study found that 48% of children in the Limpopo region were stunted.[60] Thus, the high level of poverty and the rural status of these two areas are reflected in high levels of malnutrition.

Significant progress has been made in efforts to reduce child mortality worldwide. The number of deaths of children under the age of 5 in the world decreased from about 12 million in 1990 to 6.9 million in 2011; and the global under-five mortality rate has fallen by 41 percent since 1990—from 87 deaths per 1,000 live births in 1990 to 51 in 2011. The leading causes of death among children under 5 years of age are zotiljam (18 percent), preterm labor (14 percent), diarrhea (11 percent), complications during childbirth (9 percent) and malaria (7 percent). Globally, more than a third of children under 5 are malnourished. Africa has also seen some progress over the decades. Compared to other regions, sub-Saharan Africa has seen a faster decline in under-5 mortality, with the annual rate of decline doubling between 1990-2000 and 2000-2011.[4] However, child mortality rates in sub-Saharan Africa are still remembered. In 2011, under-5 mortality (WHO, 2012) was estimated by the region alone, which equates to 9,000 children dying every day and six children dying every minute.[1] Of the 3 million newborn deaths worldwide, approximately 1.1 million are in sub-Saharan Africa (WHO, 2012).[1] The highest child mortality rates are in sub-Saharan Africa, where 1 in 9 children die under the age of 5; and one in 16 children in South Asia. Lack of essential nutrients and trace elements

Provided; Considering that vitamin A is very important for the proper functioning of the visual system and for maintaining immune protection, its deficiency remains a health problem. An estimated 250,000 to 500,000 vitamin A-deficient children become blind each year, half of whom die within 12 months of losing their sight. This deficiency accounts for 350 million cases of blindness and 670,000 deaths worldwide (WHO, 2001). In Africa alone, it contributes to 23% of child deaths. In 2009, the low prevalence of serum retinol, associated with vitamin A deficiency, was 37.7 percent in Ethiopia, 49 percent in Congo, and 42 percent in Madagascar. The direct causes of this deficiency are the low level of consumption of animal products, the level of bioavailability of vitamin A in cereal diets, the consumption of green leaves with low leaves. lipid increased demand for vitamin A and increased body demand due to infections that often affect African children

(Manga, 2021). Equally troubling levels are present in zinc deficiencies, and this has serious adverse effects on growth, risk and severity of infection, and levels of immune function. Although the true prevalence is unclear, zinc deficiency is recognized as one of the major risk factors for morbidity and mortality. It contributes to more than 450,000 deaths per year in children under 5, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. It covered 57 percent of children under 5 in Senegal, 72 percent in Burkina Faso, and 41.5 percent in Nigeria in 2004. In children, the main causes of this deficiency are a lack of easily absorbed zinc in foods (such as meat, poultry, seafood) and an overconsumption of foods that inhibit zinc absorption, such as grains, roots and tubers. , which is one of the staples of Africa.

Disadvantages iodine, on the other hand, disrupts the synthesis of thyroid hormones, which are essential for the normal development and proper functioning of the brain and nervous system, as well as for saving body heat and energy. Iodine deficiency leads to endemic disease Goethe and cretinism among them; At the same time, retardation of mental and physical development. Globally, 1.6 million people are at risk of iodine deficiency diseases and 50 million children are affected by them. About 100,000 children are born with mental retardation every year, most of them in Africa. This is due to low consumption of iodine-rich foods (such as seafood) and excessive consumption of foods that cause bitterness, especially cassava, which is a staple in Central Africa.

Anemia is very common in Africa, especially among young children, mainly due to a diet low in animal-based foods and high in fiber-rich grains, tannins and phytates inhibiting iron absorption. In 2006, approximately 67.6 percent of children under the age of 5, and a total of 83.5 million children, were anemic.[8] Through its effects on metabolic processes such as oxygen transport, oxidative metabolism and cell growth, iron deficiency also delays growth and development. It weakens the immune system and increases susceptibility to infection, delays motor development, and reduces concentration (impairs cognitive and behavioral abilities). It therefore prevents 40-60% of African children from developing their full mental capacity. In

addition, the 26 health risks reported by the WHO Global Burden of Disease Project rank ninth in terms of years of life lost due to iron deficiency.

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